

method⁸. Solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. A 1% solution of diphenylcarbazide (B.D.H.) in absolute ethanol and a 0.5% solution of α -picoline in distilled water were employed as the reagents. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade salts.

Procedure: To an aliquot of the standard aqueous solution containing 1-30 μg of rhodium, 0.5% α -picoline (1 ml) was added and the mixture was made upto 10 ml with water ($\text{pH } 7.4 \pm 0.1$). To this, 1% diphenylcarbazide solution (1 ml) was added and the mixture was heated for 15 min in a boiling water-bath. After cooling, the solution was extracted in a separatory funnel for 5 min with MIBK (10 ml). The organic phase was separated and absorbance of the complex was measured at 560 nm against pure solvent. The rhodium contents were computed from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The bluish violet rhodium complex with diphenylcarbazide in presence of α -picoline extractable into MIBK, absorbs at λ_{max} 560 nm and obeys Beer's law over the concentration range of 1-30 μg of rhodium per 10 ml of organic phase. The reagent blank shows no absorbance at 560 nm. Hence, the absorbance of the complex is measured against pure solvent. The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction is $0.0026 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity is $4.01 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The effect of varying reagents concentration on extraction of rhodium was studied. 1 ml of 1% diphenylcarbazide solution and 1 ml of 0.5% α -picoline are adequate for complete extraction of the complex for the range of the concentration of rhodium (1-30 μg) determined. A 0.1-1% solution of α -picoline can be used without any effect on the values of absorbance. Increased diphenylcarbazide concentration also produces no significant effect. For complete colour development, 15 min heating of the metal-ligands mixture in a boiling water-bath is necessary. The colour of the complex is stable for more than 2 h, and 5 min shaking period is adequate for complete extraction. Benzene, toluene, amyl alcohol, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane and MIBK were tested as solvent for the extraction but MIBK was found to be the most effective solvent.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of diverse ions was studied by adding different amounts of foreign ions to 10 μg of rhodium(III) and determining rhodium following the extraction procedure. It was found that Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , V^{V} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pt^{IV} , fluoride, bromide, iodide, cyanide, sulphate, nitrate, nitrite, tartrate, acetate, citrate and EDTA did not interfere even when present in five-fold excess of rhodium and a good recovery of rhodium (within 3% error in microgram level) was achieved. However, equal amounts of Pd^{II} ,

Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Cr^{III} , Cr^{VI} , Ir^{III} , Ag^{I} , Au^{III} , oxalate, and thiocyanate, and five-fold excess of Ru^{III} and Os^{IV} interfere. Equal amounts of Ru^{III} and Os^{IV} do not interfere. Interference due to Cu^{II} can be removed by using EDTA and that due to Pd^{II} by using KI as masking agents. In presence of twenty-fold excess of KBr, both Ag^{I} and Au^{III} do not interfere.

The standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the absorbance was found to be 0.0042 and 0.54%, respectively for 20 μg of rhodium.

A comparison of the present method with some of the earlier methods shows that the present method is more sensitive⁴ and simple.

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References

1. F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", D. Van Nostrand, London, 1955, Vol. III, p. 480.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th. ed., E.L.B.S., 1978, p. 788.
3. F. P. TREADWELL and W. T. HALL, "Analytical Chemistry", 9th ed., John Wiley, London, 1951, p. 146.
4. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 770.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Traces of Sulphite in Sugar Samples

S. P. CHATTOPADHYAY and ARABINDA K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104

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A number of spectrophotometric methods for the determination of sulphite have been reported in the literature which involve the use of either rosaniline or pararosaniline hydrochloride dyes¹⁻⁷. The use of crystal violet (N,N,N' -hexamethylpararosaniline) dye for the determination of sulphite has been reported here. The method has been studied in details in comparison to earlier works^{8,9}. The proposed method has been applied for the determination of sulphur dioxide in white sugar samples. The composition of the sulphite-crystal violet compound has also been determined.

Experimental

Crystal violet (Sigma) was used to prepare a 0.008 M stock solution in 25% (v/v) ethanol-water. A 0.0048 M stock sulphite solution was prepared by dissolving reagent grade $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_5$ (E. Merck) in double-distilled water. A 0.25 M formaldehyde

NOTES

(E. Merck) solution was used. All other chemicals used were reagent grade. All aqueous solutions were made using double-distilled water.

Absorbance measurements were made in a Beckmann 26 spectrophotometer.

Standard procedure: Crystal violet (0.5 ml, 0.008 M), KCl (4.0 ml, 0.1 M) and HCl (2.0 ml, 0.8 M) were mixed in a 10 ml volumetric flask and allowed to stand for 30 min for the discharge of the colour of crystal violet. Then formaldehyde solution (0.5 ml, 0.25 M) and various amounts of standard sulphite solution (4.8×10^{-4} M) were added. The resulting mixture was allowed to develop its colour in 9 min and the volume was made up to the mark with double-distilled water. Finally, the absorbance values were measured within 10 min after the colour development at 605 nm using a reagent blank as reference.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance spectra: The absorbance values of several aliquots containing known amounts of sulphite were recorded at 675-550 nm using reagent blanks as references. $\lambda_{\max}$ was found at 605 nm and the molar absorptivity 2.46×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Calibration curve: Working curves were prepared by the standard procedure. Beer's law is followed in the range 0.032-3.895 μ g sulphite per ml. According to Sandell¹⁰ the optimum concentration range is 0.739-2.550 μ g per ml.

Optimisation of acidity, amount of formaldehyde and reagent concentration: Acidity of 0.23 to 0.11 M HCl was maintained during the determination of sulphite by the present method. 0.3 to 0.9 ml of 0.25 M formaldehyde solution should be present to determine 1.00 to 3 $\times$.00 μ g of sulphite per 10 ml of the resulting mixture. For the same amount of sulphite determination, experiments using 0.50 ml of the reagent solution showed that 1.58 mg of crystal violet was sufficient for the quantitative determination.

Effect of diverse ions: The tolerance limits for different diverse ions (within an error of $\pm 2\%$) were studied, and the results indicate that for the determination of 21.94 μ g sulphite per 10 ml no interference is caused by 3000 μ g chloride; 2500 μ g nitrate; 2000 μ g sulphate, thiocyanate, Na, K, ammonium; 1000 μ g EDTA, Zn^{II}; 500 μ g Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, bromide; 400 μ g acetate; 200 μ g Fe^{III}, Ca^{II}. Only thiosulphate, nitrite, Hg^{II} ions have been found to interfere.

Sensitivity of method: The Sandell sensitivity¹⁰ was found to be 0.003 μ g cm⁻². Sensitivity of the present method is better than that of the widely used West and Gaeke method⁹. The relative standard deviation was $\pm 0.769\%$ for 4 determinations while the confidence limit (95%) was 1.990 ± 0.041 μ g sulphite per ml.

Application to sugar samples: Sulphite ion liberated from the white sugar samples by a base, is added to acidic crystal violet for colour development. Addition of NaOH solution liberates the chemically bound SO₂ entrapped during the bleaching of raw sugar¹¹. Formaldehyde was used to stabilise SO₂¹² in solution. White sugar (4-5 g) was taken in a 50 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in double-distilled water and the volume made up to the mark after adjusting the pH of the solution to alkaline range. An aliquot was taken and analysed by the proposed method. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SULPHITE IN SUGAR SAMPLES

Sample no.	Sugar taken g/50 ml	Amount of aliquot analysed ml	Absorbance	SO ₂ ⁻ found** mg/kg sugar
1	5.0110	(a) 2.0	0.195	19.98
		(b) 4.0	0.225	
2	5.0047	(a) 2.0	0.195	23.20
		(b) 4.0	0.288	
3	4.9820	(a) 2.0	0.280	57.97
		(b) 4.0	0.560	

* Collected from different stores.

** Average of determinations (a) and (b).

Nature of the sulphite crystal violet reaction product: The colour of the crystal violet cation is due to the chromophore in its canonical form. On the other hand, when a suitable nucleophile (e.g. HSO₃⁻) is present at sufficiently high concentration, it adds to the central carbon atom of the cation, leading to the loss of the chromophoric canonical forms and consequent loss of colour. A similar loss of colour occurs at high pH due to the formation of the carbinol. However, the addition of bisulphite ion has been established to result in bonding *via* sulphur rather than oxygen, leading to a sulphonic acid¹³. Although an aminocarbinol seemed to be the first intermediate which would undergo subsequent nucleophilic substitution by sulphite ion¹³.

The composition of the coloured species was determined by the mole-ratio method¹⁴ and the curve indicated that the compound contains crystal violet cation and bisulphite ion in the ratio 1 : 1. The value of the degree of dissociation was calculated by Harvey and Manning's equation¹⁵, and the stability constant was found to be 2.68×10^8 . The stability constant was also verified with the help of Rossotti and Rossotti's method¹⁶ which gave the value 1.22×10^8 .

References

1. A. STEIGMANN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, **22**, 492.
2. P. URONE, W. E. BOGGS and C. M. NOYES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 1517.
3. P. W. WEST and G. C. GAERKE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 1816.
4. J. B. PATE, J. P. LODGE and A. F. WARTBURG, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 1660.

5. S. BARABAS and J. KAMINSKI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **35**, 1702.
6. F. P. SCARINGELLI, B. E. SALTZMAN and S. A. FREY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, **39**, 1709.
7. H. G. C. KING and G. PRUDEN, *Analyst*, 1969, **94**, 48.
8. E. RAMANAUSKAS, V. TUTKUVIENE, L. BUNIKIENE, K. GRIGONIENE and A. ZEBRAUSKAITE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, **86**, 37205.
9. W. L. HINZE, D. J. KIPPENBERGER and R. E. HUMPHREY, *Microchem. J.*, 1975, **20**, 43.
10. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Trace Metals", 3rd edn., Interscience, New York, 1959, pp. 88, 97.
11. M. GAWRYCH and A. BUTWILOWICZ, *Gas. Cukrow*, 1969, **77**, 8 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, **71**, 51459).
12. P. K. DASGUPTA, K. DECHSAR and J. C. ULLRBY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1980, **52**, 1912.
13. T. S. CAMERON and W. J. CHUTE, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1979, **35**, 325.
14. J. H. YOK and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
15. A. E. HARVRY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
16. F. J. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, "The Determination of Stability Constant", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1961, p. 275.

Determination of Acetone in Aqueous Solution

S. FALAMERZ, A. K. HAREEZ and W. A. BASHIR*

Department of Chemistry, College of Science,
University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

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accepted 30 August 1985

ACETONE in aqueous solution has been determined with various but unsatisfactory chromogens^{1,2}, since they resort to rigorous conditions for the quantitative determination of acetone. Under suitable conditions, acetone has been found to react sensitively and selectively with diazotised *p*-aminobenzoic acid to give a purple colour, which is stable in the presence of starch.

Experimental

The 1.5% diazotised *p*-aminobenzoic acid solution was prepared as described elsewhere³. The 200 ppm acetone solution was prepared in distilled water. The absorption measurements were made with a Shimadzu UV-210 A double-beam spectrophotometer and Baush & Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer. Sodium hydroxide (35%) and starch (0.05%) solutions were prepared in distilled water.

Procedure: To an aliquot of sample solution (10-180 μ g of acetone) in a 20 ml volumetric flask, were added reagent solution (2 ml), sodium hydroxide solution (2 ml), starch solution (2 ml) and distilled water to the mark. After 25 min, the absorbance of the purple coloured solution was measured against the reagent blank, within another 15 min, at 530 nm using 1 cm cells. The amount of acetone was deduced from the calibration curve prepared from 10-180 μ g of acetone.

Results and Discussion

Colour reaction and absorption spectrum: In alkaline medium, α -hydrogen containing compounds couple with diazonium salts to produce coloured chromophores³⁻⁵. This forms the basis of the method. When dilute solution of acetone and diazotised *p*-aminobenzoic acid reagent are mixed in the presence of alkali, a purple coloured compound formed which has an absorbance maximum at 530 nm. This wavelength is adopted in all subsequent experiments.

Effect of starch: The purple colour decays upon dilution with water. To overcome such difficulty, reducing agents and protective colloids were tried. Reducing agents are unsatisfactory since they changed the purple colour to a less intense yellow. Of the surfactant tested, 2 ml of 0.05% starch solution, when introduced after all other reagents and before dilution to the mark, is found to stabilise the colour for 15 min after 25 min development period. The amount of reagent and sodium hydroxide were of 2 ml each.

Under the above conditions, Beer's law adheres to solutions containing up to 180 μ g of acetone per 20 ml, with a molar absorptivity of $6.2 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The accuracy of this method (range 10-180 μ g of acetone) is found to be +4.1 to +0.31 with a corresponding standard deviation percent of 6.62-1.01 (five determinations). The interfering effect of some foreign compounds was studied, and their tolerable amounts (ppm) in the presence of 5 ppm acetone, are: acetaldehyde (2), acetoacetic acid (20), amyl alcohol (15), aniline (85), benzaldehyde (60), chloroform (65), cyclohexanone (15), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (13), dioxan (40), ethanol (15), ethyl acetate (55), ethyl acetoacetate (12), formaldehyde (70), formic acid (50), lactic acid (25), methanol (50) and propanol (20). These figures correspond to the amount of foreign compounds causing an error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance reading.

The present method is simple, rapid, sensitive and selective. It is more simple than the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine and the salicylaldehyde methods and also, more sensitive than the former.

References

1. J. AHMADZADEH and J. H. HARKER, *Microchem. J.*, 1974, **19**, 279.
2. S. BERNTSSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 1937.
3. S. A. RAHIM and W. A. BASHIR, *Analyst*, 1979, **104**, 466.
4. W. A. BASHIR and S. FALAMERZ, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1981, **309**, 401.
5. W. A. BASHIR, G. W. HAGOP and S. FALAMERZ, *Microchem. J.*, 1982, **27**, 00.